

THE ROLE OF LINGVOCULTUREME IN THE STUDY OF NATIONAL AND CULTURAL FEATURES OF SPEECH UNITS.

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Annotation: It is obvious that Linguocultureme has a broader concept than reality and lacuna, and has a plan of content and expression. Linguacultural can include phraseological units, phrases, pares, complex syntactic units, sentences, texts, which are an integral part of culture. When we compare linguacultural with words, we see that they have a deeper, deeper and broader meaning than words. For this reason, we include in it units of language, such as phraseological units, word combinations, which express forms and semantically complex meanings.

Keywords: speech, concept, phraseological units, syntactic units, combinations.

Commenting on the meaning of linguacultural, O. Yusupov said that "the semantics of linguacultural includes words, phraseological units, phrases, sentences, parems, speech clichés, complex syntactic units, texts, etc., which reflect a part of culture.[1.2].

It can be concluded that linguacultural is specific to a particular nation or people, expresses the interdependence of language and culture, combines linguistic and nonlinguistic factors, and, as noted above, manifests itself in any unit of language. is the object of lingvoculturology. AE Mamatov says about linguoculturema: "Linguoculturema reflects the linguistic and extralinguistic dialectical unity, which includes the concept and the subject matter. Dialectical communication in the process of understanding the object requires, on the one hand, the linguistic and non-linguistic components of lingvocultureme, their inequalities,

differences, and, on the other hand, their compatibility, exact similarity. As an integral part of linguacultural, language informs not only about its "superficial" meaning, but also that its "complete" content is the basis (element, segment) of culture "[1.3]. Below we will try to consider the national and cultural words that exist in our speech, that is, each of the inter-level language units of the event on the basis of empirical examples Safari, sari, currency, samurai, money, ruble, kopeck, shilling, pound, sterling, pence, penny, cent, borsh, chops, barbeque, drugstore, cloverleaf, sponge, cuckoo's call, kimano, lord, jazz, rock, pop, mosque, parliament, abbot, cabin, pound, frank, kuyoykochdi, atala, surpaochdi, surpaqoqdi, wrapping, dimlama, boiling, sum, coin, dough, yolk, mullajiring, dollar, etc.

Some of the words are an integral part of Uzbek culture and language like ours. These are completely incomprehensible realities for other peoples and nations that are not our brothers. This is mainly due to the fact that cognitive semantics is specific to the thinking of a certain group of language speakers, and may be unknown, insignificant, or unnecessary to others. The most important of these concepts are cultural, cultural background, cultural concept, and cultural connotation, which can be expressed through the linguistic units of cultural information. The term *lingvoculturema* began to be used in scientific research.

Lingvoculturemes (meaning of language-nominative meaning, subject meaning), as well as national-cultural (non-linguistic cultural meaning). A word (sign-meaning) as a unit of language is an integral part of *lingvocultureme*. If the word represents the events in the language, *lingvocultureme* represents the content of the subject. *Lingvocultureme* can be expressed in words, sentences, terms, phrases, depending on the language. *Lingvocultureme* is a complex phenomenon in relation to language unity. It expresses the expression of language, along with the imagination, the environment outside the language (situation, reality), existence. Any person who is fluent in their mother tongue or other foreign language has a cultural meaning in their speech. Without a cultural meaning, we cannot enter into the essence of this or that text, we cannot comprehend its content. We cannot understand the

cultural phenomenon in the context of the text. Knowledge of the national mentality is necessary to imagine the uniqueness of a nation. Linguoculture, while expressing its own nominative meaning, provides an opportunity to understand the cultural-enlightenment, national mentality and associative ideas. Researchers have long been interested in the semantics of linguocultures, as they reflect the customs and traditions, culture, history, way of life, national cultural features of a particular people in connection with the economic environment. The science of linguoculturology, which has a more practical nature, became more relevant in the XIX century, when the study of linguistic phenomena as a product of the anthropological paradigm began. By the last quarter of the XX century schools of linguoculturology Yu.S. Stepanov, N.D. Arutyunova, V.N. Teliya, V. Vorobev, V. Shaklenay were formed. In addition to the above, it can be said that linguoculturology is a field that directly and indirectly deals with the nation and its values, and this, of course, is reflected in its language. As V.A. Maslova noted, “language is the verbal treasure of the nation”. [7]

1. Tandir – a special clay oven for baking bread; to build an oven, to light a fire in the oven, to bake bread in the oven. There is no in the house, there is a double tandir on the roof (proverb).

2. Atlas – one side glossy, floral, local silk fabric.

3. Belbog` – a piece of fabric with or without flowers in the shape of a rectangular scarf, which can be tied at the waist. Are you young and proud of your youth? In the sense of [7.28]

4. Beshik – A special four-legged device designed to hold and shake the baby to sleep. To shake the cradle is to cherish, to develop, to contribute to that field. Did you shake my cradle? _ to be ungrateful to oneself

5. Qumg`on – a teapot-shaped vessel, often made of copper; tea pot, copper sandstone, cast iron sandstone [7.62]

6. To`n – 1. Bought open long top national dress; chopon. 2. To act according to something or someone. Everyone dances according to himself. 3. To enter the

night – to enter the appearance, the color. 4. To put on the cloak upside down - to be angry with someone or something, to work, to be upset.

7. Do'ppi- (scullcup). An aura-lined, often floral, plate-shaped, floral or non-floral hat with a sloping top and a hem. If the head survives, the doppia will be found. (Proverbs.) There is aman under the doppia. (Proverbs). When the doppia is narrow 1. when the work is urgent or unavoidable.

8. Atala- 1. A liquid dish cooked with flour and water on a heated side. 2. Mobile. Such a liquid thing as food. 3. Atala is about a very loose, lazy, lazy person.

9. Lapar- A national song sung by boys and girls at weddings and gatherings.

10. O`choq- 1. A device that is usually closed on three sides, with a fire inside and a

cooking pot on top. 2. Mobile. The place, source, center where something appears, takes place, spreads. The hearth of knowledge, the hearth of enlightenment.

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